

Participant name	Date	Description name	Description type	Description Area	Description location	Description duration (days)	Male attenders	Female attenders	Non-binary attenders	Total attenders
BU-ISCIII Sara Monzón Fernández	21/02/2024	Git, Github & Github actions	Online-Training	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	10	6		16
BU-ISCIII Sarai Varona Fernández	03/05/2024	Viral genome reconstruction using viralrecon	Online-Training	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	13	10		23
BU-ISCIII Sarai Varona Fernández	09/05/2024	Viral genome reconstruction using IRMA	Online-Training	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	12	11		23
Organized by BU-ISCIII José Antonio Boga & José María González Alba (Hospital Universitario Central Asturias)	17/09/2024	Bioinformatics workflow	On-line monthly meeting	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	18	9		27
Organized by BU-ISCIII Samuel S. Shepard (CDC-Atlanta USA)	02/10/2024	IRMA the Iterative Refinement Meta-Assembler	Online-Training	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	19	11		30
Organized by BU-ISCIII Alejandra González (HUVall d'Hebron)	08/10/2024	Bioinformatics workflow	On-line monthly meeting	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	19	13		32
Organized by BU-ISCIII Alejandro Sanz Carbonell	26/11/2024	Optimización del uso de secuenciación Oxford-Nanopore en Vigilancia Genómica	Online-Training	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	21	18		39
Organized by BU-ISCIII Javier Lopez Florido y María Lara (Computational MedicinePlatform / Fundación Progreso y Salud, Junta Andalucía)	19/12/2024	Bioinformatics workflow	On-line monthly meeting	Bioinformatics	On-line	1hour	18	12		30
Organized by BU-ISCIII nf-core Hackathon Madrid Local Site	24-26/03/2025	nf-core Hackathon	Hackathon	Bioinformatics	Madrid	3days	8	10		18
Alejandro Bernabeu BU-ISCIII	27/11/2025	relecov-tools demo	On-line monthly meeting	Bioinformatics	On-line	1h 45min	11	9		20